

Synthesis and Characterisation of Heterocyclic Semicarbazones and their Aluminium(III) Complexes

NIKHILESH CHANDRA BHARDWAJ and R. V. SINGH*

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004

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Metal complexes of semicarbazones have recently attracted special attention due to their biological activities¹. These ligands are also interesting as only the β -nitrogen coordinates to the metal atom. Although a large number of references are available on the complexes of ligands derived from heterocyclic aldehydes², but there has been no work on the aluminium(III) complexes with these ligands. It was therefore, considered of interest to synthesise such derivatives by reacting aluminium isopropoxide with these ligands.

Results and Discussion

The reactions of aluminium(III) isopropoxide and monobasic bidentate ligands (LH) were carried out in three molar ratios (1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3) in dry benzene. Successive replacement of isopropoxy groups by the ligands resulted in the formation of products of the types $\text{AlX}_2(\text{L})$, $\text{AlX}(\text{L})_2$ and $\text{AlX}(\text{L})_3$ (where X is isopropoxy group),

where $n=1, 2$ and 3 .

The complexes are coloured solids, soluble in benzene, chloroform, DMSO and THF. The mono- and bis-isopropoxy complexes are moisture-sensitive and readily hydrolyse when kept in the open atmosphere, while the tris-ligand-metal derivatives are quite stable and do not hydrolyse under similar conditions.

The molecular weights of these complexes indicate the mono- and bis-isopropoxy complexes to be dimeric, whereas the tris-ligand-metal complexes as monomeric in nature. The dimerisation in these

derivatives was considered to involve isopropoxy bridges³.

The semicarbazones exhibit a strong band at $\sim 1590 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to C=N stretch. The complex exhibit this vibration at higher frequency $1615 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, indicating the coordination of the azomethine nitrogen to the aluminium atom⁴. The absence of ν_{NH} mode around 3140 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the complexes also suggests the deprotonation of this group. Two strong bands due to symmetric and asymmetric vibrations of NH_2 in the region $3400\text{--}3500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, remain unaltered in the corresponding metal complexes, indicating their non-involvement in coordination.

The complexes exhibit new bands at $610\text{--}630$ and $460\text{--}590 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be attributed to the different vibrational modes of $\nu_{\text{Al-O}^i}$ ⁵ and $\nu_{\text{Al-N}}^6$, respectively. In the ^1H nmr spectra, the disappearance of the NH resonance signal of the ligand cinnamaldehyde semicarbazone (δ 11.86) in the complexes, provides the evidence of complexation. The azomethine proton signal observed at δ 8.20 in the ligand is shifted downfield in the case of the complexes and appear at δ 8.68 (1 : 1), 8.48 (1 : 2) and 8.42 (1 : 3), indicating the coordination of azomethine nitrogen to the central metal atom. Amino resonance signal (δ 2.48) remains at almost the same position (δ 2.10–2.56 ppm) in the metal complexes, indicating its non-involvement in the complexation. The disappearance of isopropoxy resonance signals from the region δ 1.04 and 4.34 and appearance of t-butoxy signal at δ 1.20 indicate the replacement of isopropoxy groups by t-butoxy groups in the replacement products. The azomethine proton signals in the t-butoxy complexes appear at δ 8.36 (1 : 2) and 8.32 (1 : 1).

In the ^{13}C nmr spectra, the shifting in the positions of the amido (from δ 188.21 to 170.43–171.17) and azomethine carbons (from δ 176.56 to 155.09–157.80) suggests the coordination of oxygen and nitrogen to the central metal atom.

Based on the above spectral data a penta-coordinated environment may be proposed for the 1:1 aluminium complexes and hexa-coordinated environment for the 1:2 and 1:3 aluminium complexes.

(1 : 1 Product)

(1 : 2 Product)

(1 : 3 Product)

where $\overbrace{\text{O N}}$ represents the donor system of the ligand.

Experimental

All the reactions were carried out under strictly anhydrous condition. The ligands were prepared by the method reported earlier⁷ and recrystallised before use.

To aluminium(III) isopropoxide (0.75–1.44 g) in dry benzene (~60 ml), the ligand (0.92–2.64 g) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 10–34 h. The completion of the reaction was confirmed by the amount of isopropanol liberated during the reaction as an azeotrope with benzene. The solvent was then removed and the residue was dried under reduced pressure at 40–60° for 2–3 h (Table 1).

The benzene solution of mono- and bis-isopropoxy aluminium(III) complexes was mixed with Bu^tOH (1 or 2 mol). The progress of the reaction

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF ALUMINIUM(III) COMPLEXES

Compd.	M.p. (°C)/ (Colour)	Analyses % : Found (Calcd.)				
		C	H	N	S	Al
$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4\text{Al}$	305d (Yellow)	48.21 (48.48)	6.56 (6.78)	14.09 (14.13)	—	9.04 (9.07)
$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_4\text{O}_5\text{Al}$	245d (Yellow)	45.84 (46.16)	4.81 (4.91)	21.47 (21.53)	—	6.82 (6.91)
$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_6\text{O}_6\text{Al}$	212 (Yellow)	44.53 (44.73)	3.69 (3.75)	26.01 (26.08)	—	5.46 (5.58)
$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3\text{SAl}$	325d (White)	45.87 (45.99)	6.38 (6.43)	13.39 (13.41)	10.11 (10.23)	8.74 (8.61)
$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_6\text{O}_3\text{S}_2\text{Al}$	225d (White)	42.19 (42.65)	4.59 (4.53)	19.82 (19.89)	15.04 (15.18)	6.50 (6.38)
$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_6\text{O}_3\text{S}_3\text{Al}$	221d (White)	40.56 (40.67)	3.29 (3.41)	23.69 (23.71)	18.00 (18.09)	5.18 (5.08)
$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_6\text{O}_3\text{Al}$	290d (Yellow)	57.42 (57.65)	7.18 (7.26)	12.62 (12.60)	—	8.23 (8.09)
$\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{27}\text{N}_6\text{O}_3\text{Al}$	250d (Yellow)	59.66 (59.73)	5.77 (5.82)	18.15 (18.17)	—	5.97 (5.83)
$\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_9\text{O}_3\text{Al}$	206d (Yellow)	60.81 (60.91)	5.02 (5.11)	21.28 (21.31)	—	4.50 (4.56)
$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_6\text{O}_3\text{Al}$	268d (Cream)	55.36 (55.43)	6.71 (6.69)	16.15 (16.17)	—	7.63 (7.79)
$\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{25}\text{N}_6\text{O}_3\text{Al}$	207d (Cream)	56.41 (56.55)	5.02 (5.16)	22.91 (22.94)	—	5.44 (5.52)
$\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{27}\text{N}_{12}\text{O}_3\text{Al}$	202d (Cream)	57.01 (57.14)	4.22 (4.31)	26.66 (26.65)	—	4.19 (4.28)

was followed by estimating isopropanol in the binary azeotrope and the resulting compound was dried at 40–60° under reduced pressure for 2–3 h (Table 2).

TABLE 2—EXCHANGE REACTIONS OF MONO- and BIS-ISOPROPOXY ALUMINIUM(III) COMPLEXES, $\text{Al(X)}(\text{L})_2$ and $\text{Al(X)}_2(\text{L})$ WITH Bu^tOH

Compd.	M.p. (°C)/ (Colour)	Analyses % : Found/Calcd.)		
		Al	N	S
$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_6\text{O}_5\text{Al}$	270d (Brown)	6.59 (6.67)	20.75 (20.78)	—
$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_5\text{O}_4\text{Al}$	225d (Yellow)	8.33 (8.29)	12.97 (12.91)	—
$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_6\text{O}_3\text{S}_2\text{Al}$	210d (Yellow)	6.20 (6.18)	19.27 (19.25)	14.72 (14.69)
$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3\text{SAl}$	220d (Cream)	7.92 (7.90)	12.33 (12.31)	9.42 (9.39)
$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{29}\text{N}_6\text{O}_3\text{Al}$	270d (Yellow)	5.67 (5.66)	17.68 (17.64)	—
$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_6\text{O}_3\text{Al}$	322d (Yellow)	7.49 (7.46)	11.68 (11.63)	—
$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{27}\text{N}_6\text{O}_3\text{Al}$	220d (Brown)	5.39 (5.37)	22.34 (22.30)	—
$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{27}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3\text{Al}$	250d (Brown)	7.24 (7.21)	14.99 (14.96)	—

Isopropanol in the azeotrope was determined by an oxidimetric method and aluminium was estimated as aluminium oxinate. Carbon and hydrogen analyses were carried out at the Microanalytical Laboratory of the Department. Nitrogen was determined by the Kjeldahl's method. Sulphur was determined as barium sulphate by Messenger's method.

Molecular weights were determined in THF by the Ebullioscopic method. Ir spectra (nujol/KBr)

were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and ^1H and ^{13}C nmr spectra on a Jeol FX-90 Q spectrometer in DMSO-d_6 and benzene using TMS as the internal standard.

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References

1. N. ORLOVA, V. A. AKSENOVA, V. A. SCLIDOVKIN, N. S. BAGDANOVA and G. N. PERKIN, *Russ. Pharm. Toxicol.*, 1968, 348; D. J. BAVER, L. S. VINCENT, C. H. KEMPE and A. W. DOWNIE, *Lancet.*, 1963, 20, 494; H. G. PETERING, H. H. BUSKIK and G. E. UNDERWOOD, *Cancer Res.*, 1964, 64, 367.
2. S. CHANDRA, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1983, 13, 89; N. KANOONGO, R. V. SINGH and J. P. TANDON, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1987, 17, 837; A. GARG and J. P. TANDON, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1988, 18, 705; K. SINGH, R. V. SINGH and J. P. TANDON, *Polyhedron*, 1988, 7, 151; *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1988, 330, 621; V. P. SINGH and R. V. SINGH, *Nat. Acad. Sci. Lett.*, 1989, 12, 311.
3. D. C. BRADLEY, R. C. MEHROTRA and D. P. GAUR, "Metal Alkoxides", Academic, London, 1978, p. 219.
4. M. AGARWAL, J. P. TANDON and R. C. MEHROTRA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1979, 41, 1405.
5. K. K. CHATURVEDI, R. V. SINGH and J. P. TANDON, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1985, 327, 144.
6. K. K. CHATURVEDI, R. V. SINGH and J. P. TANDON, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, 23, 754.
7. N. KANOONGO, R. V. SINGH and J. P. TANDON, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1988, 13, 343.